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THESAURUS AND QUERY EXPANSION

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ABSTRACT

The explosive growth of the World Wide Web is making it difficult for a user to locate information that is relevant to his/her interest. Though existing search engines work well to a certain extent but they still face problems like word mismatch which arises because the majority of information retrieval systems compare query and document terms on lexical level rather than on semantic level and short query: the average length of queries by the user is less than two words. Short queries and the incompatibility between the terms in user queries and documents strongly affect the retrieval of relevant document. Query expansion has long been suggested as a technique to increase the effectiveness of the information retrieval. Query expansion is the process of supplementing additional terms or phrases to the original query to improve the retrieval performance. The central problem of query expansion is the selection of the expansion terms based on which user's original query is expanded. Thesaurus helps to solve this problem. Thesaurus have frequently been incorporated in information retrieval system for identifying the synonymous expressions and linguistic entities that are semantically similar. Thesaurus has been widely used in many applications, including information retrieval and natural language processing.

KEYWORDS

Network Protocols, Wireless Network, Mobile Network, Virus, Worms &Trojon Thesaurus, Automatic query expansion, Local context analysis, Information retrieval

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Text Independent Speaker Recognition and Speaker Independent Speech Recognition Using Iterative Clustering Approach

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the effectiveness of perceptual features and iterative clustering approach for performing both speech and speaker recognition. Procedure used for formation of training speech is different for developing training models for speaker independent speech and text independent speaker recognition. So, this work mainly emphasizes the utilization of clustering models developed for the training data to obtain better accuracy as 91%, 91% and 99.5% for mel frequency perceptual linear predictive cepstrum with respect to three categories such as speaker identification, isolated digit recognition and continuous speech recognition. This feature also produces 9% as low equal error rate which is used as a performance measure for speaker verification. The work is experimentally evaluated on the set of isolated digits and continuous speeches from TI digits_1 and TI digits_2 database for speech recognition and on speeches of 50 speakers randomly chosen from TIMIT database for speaker recognition. The noteworthy feature of speaker recognition algorithm is to evaluate the testing procedure on identical messages of all the 50 speakers, theoretical validation of results using F-ratio and validation of results by statistical analysis using 2χ distribution.

Keywords:

Clustering methods, Speech recognition, Speaker recognition, Spectral analysis, Speech analysis, Speech processing, Vector quantization.

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IDENTIFICATION OF TELUGU, DEVANAGARI AND ENGLISH SCRIPTS USING DISCRIMINATING FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

In a multi-script multi-lingual environment, a document may contain text lines in more than one script/language forms. It is necessary to identify different script regions of the document in order to feed the document to the OCRs of individual language. With this context, this paper proposes to develop a model to identify and separate text lines of Telugu, Devanagari and English scripts from a printed trilingual document. The proposed method uses the distinct features extracted from the top and bottom profiles of the printed text lines. Experimentation conducted involved 1500 text lines for learning and 900 text lines for testing. The performance has turned out to be 99.67%.

KEYWORDS

Multi-script multi-lingual document, Script Identification, Feature extraction.

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ANALYSIS ON DEPLOYMENT COST AND NETWORK PERFORMANCE FOR HETEROGENEOUS WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

A wireless sensor network is an autonomous system of sensor connected by wireless devices without any fixed infrastructure support. One of the major issues in wireless sensor network is developing a cost effective routing protocol which has a significant impact on the overall network performance in the sensor network. In this paper, we have considered three types of nodes with different battery energy. The key role of the proposed protocol is to maximize the network performance without increasing the network deployment cost. We have compared the quantitative analysis of different protocols in terms of their network deployment cost. Our analysis and simulation results demonstrate that the proposed scheme can achieve higher network performance and lower network deployment cost as compared to the existing protocols.

KEYWORDS

Heterogeneous, Clustering, Cost, Lifetime, Sensor Networks

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Analysis of Telecommunication Management Technologies

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenal success of IT and Telecommunication would not have been possible without any effective management framework. The management technologies have also been maturing with evolution of IT & Telecom. In this paper, we trace out some important traditional and current telecommunications management technologies in terms of their strengths and limitations. We analyze them in order to draw lessons and guidelines for emerging research in this field.

KEYWORDS

Network Management Technologies, Distributed Object Technologies, Web based Technologies, Autonomic services and network management vision.

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DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF 32-BIT CONTROLLER FOR INTERACTIVE INTERFACING WITH RECONFIGURABLE COMPUTING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Partial reconfiguration allows time-sharing of physical resources for the execution of multiple functional modules by swapping in or out at run-time without incurring any system downtime. This results in dramatically increase in speed and functionality of FPGA based system. This paper presents the designing an interface controller through UART for execution & implementation of reconfigurable modules (RM) on Xilinx Virtex-4(XC4VFX12), (XC4VFX20) and (XC4VFX60) devices. To verify partial reconfiguration execution at run-time an interface has been designed to make user interaction with the system at run-time. Interface design includes the controllers for controlling the flow of data to and from the reconfigurable modules to the external world (host environment) through busmacros. The controller is designed as static module. All the static as well as dynamic modules are designed and simulated to verify the functionality with supporting simulation tool using ModelSim-6.0d and synthesized with Xilinx 9.1.02i_PR10 (ISE).

KEYWORDS

Reconfigurable computing systems, Partial reconfiguration, FPGA, Reconfigurable modules, Busmacros

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ENSEMBLE DESIGN FOR INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Intrusion Detection problem is one of the most promising research issues of Information Security. The problem provides excellent opportunities in terms of providing host and network security. Intrusion detection is divided into two categories with respect to the type of detection. Misuse detection and Anomaly detection. Intrusion detection is done using rule based, Statistical, and Soft computing techniques. The rule based measures provides better results but the extensibility of the approach is still a question. The statistical measures are lagging in identifying the new types of attacks. Soft Computing Techniques offers good results since learning is done using the training, and during testing the new pattern of attacks was also recognized appreciably. This paper aims at detecting Intruders using both Misuse and Anomaly detection by applying Ensemble of soft Computing Techniques. Neural networks, Support Vector Machines and Naïve Bayes Classifiers are trained and tested individually and the classification rates for different classes are observed. Then threshold values are set for all the classes. Based on this threshold value the ensemble approach produces result for various classes. The standard kddcup'99 dataset is used in this research for Misuse detection. Shonlau dataset of truncated UNIX commands is used for Anomaly detection. The detection rate and false alarm rates are notified. Multilayer Perceptrons,

KEYWORDS

Intrusion Detection Systems, Anomaly Detection Systems, Misuse Detection Systems, Support Vector Machines, Naïve Bayes Classifiers, Multilayer Perceptrons, Ensemble approach

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Optimal Curve Fitting of Speech Signal for Disabled Children

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the amplitude profile of sampled speech data were fitted by employing sum of sine functions with a confidence level more than 90%. Furthermore, amplitude correlation technique is applied between original speech signal samples of normal and pathological subjects and correlation technique is also applied between the curve fit constant values for normal and pathological subjects. Results obtained in both the techniques were compared to determine the varying degrees of speech disability severity.

KEYWORDS

Correlation, Curve fitting, Discrete time signal, Linear filter, Speech disability

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INVESTIGATING THE PERFORMANCE OF VARIOUS VOCODERS FOR A FAIR SCHEDULING ALGORITHM IN WIMAX

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ABSTRACT

An appealing feature of blockchain technology is smart contracts. A smart contract is executable code that runs on top of the blockchain to facilitate, execute and enforce an agreement between untrusted parties without the involvement of a trusted third party. In this paper, we conduct a systematic mapping study to collect all research that is relevant to smart contracts from a technical perspective. The aim of doing so is to identify current research topics and open challenges for future studies in smart contract research. We extract 24 papers from different scientific databases. The results show that about two thirds of the papers focus on identifying and tackling smart contract issues. Four key issues are identified, namely, codifying, security, privacy and performance issues. The rest of the papers focuses on smart contract applications or other smart contract related topics. Research gaps that need to be addressed in future studies are provided.

KEYWORDS

Blockchain, Smart contracts, Systematic mapping study, Survey

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